

In-situ Electrochemical Reconstruction and Modulation of Adsorbed Hydrogen Coverage in Cobalt/Ruthenium-based Catalyst Boost Electroreduction of Nitrate to Ammonia

Jian Zhang¹, Thomas Quast¹, Bashir Eid¹, Yen-Ting Chen², Ridha Zerdoumi¹, Stefan Dieckhöfer¹, João R. C. Junqueira¹, Sabine Seisel¹, Wolfgang Schuhmann^{1*}

¹Analytical Chemistry - Center for Electrochemical Sciences (CES); Faculty of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Ruhr University Bochum; Universitätsstr. 150; D-44780 Bochum; Germany.

²Center for Solvation Science (ZEMOS), Ruhr University Bochum, Universitätsstr. 150; D-44801 Bochum, Germany

E-mail: wolfgang.schuhmann@rub.de

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Fig. S1 | Elemental compositions of the catalysts. (a) ICP-MS-determined atomic percentage of Co, Ru, and B of the synthesized catalysts. (b) XPS-determined atomic percentage of Co, Ru, and B at the surface of the synthesized catalysts.

Supplementary Fig. S2 | Particle size distribution of the catalysts. (a) TEM images of Co-B and the corresponding size distribution curve. (b) TEM images of Co-B/Ru₁₂ and the corresponding size distribution curve. (c) TEM images of Ru and the corresponding size distribution curve.

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Supplementary Fig. S11 | NH₃ synthesis performance on Co-B/Ru₁₂ at a series of potentials. (a) Chronoamperograms of Co-B/Ru₁₂ at different potentials for 1 h in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH and 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻. UV-Vis absorption spectra for the quantification of NH₃ (b) and NO₂⁻ (c). Note that for the detection of NH₄⁺, the post-electrolysis electrolytes at -0.05 V, -0.1 V, -0.15 V, -0.2 V were diluted 40 times, while that at 0 V was diluted 20 times. As for the NO₂⁻ tests, the post-electrolysis electrolytes at 0 V, -0.05 V, -0.1 V, -0.15 V, -0.2 V were diluted 25 times. (d) Faradaic efficiency (FE) of NH₃ and NO₂⁻. Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S12 | NH₃ synthesis performance on Co-B/Ru₃₈ at a series of potentials. (a) Chronoamperograms of Co-B/Ru₃₈ at different potentials for 1 h in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH and 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻. UV-Vis absorption spectra for the quantification of NH₃ (b) and NO₂⁻ (c). Note that for the detection of NH₄⁺, the post-electrolysis electrolyte at 0 V was diluted 10 times, at -0.05 V, -0.1 V were diluted 20 times, while that at -0.15 V, -0.2 V were diluted 40 times. As for the NO₂⁻ tests, the post-electrolysis electrolytes at 0 V, -0.05 V, -0.1 V, -0.15 V, -0.2 V were diluted 25 times. (d) Faradaic efficiency (FE) of NH₃ and NO₂⁻. Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S13 | NH₃ synthesis performance on Co-B/Ru₇₅ at a series of potentials. (a) Chronoamperograms of Co-B/Ru₇₅ at different potentials for 1 h in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH and 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻. UV-Vis absorption spectra for the quantification of NH₃ (b) and NO₂⁻ (c). Note that for the detection of NH₄⁺, the post-electrolysis electrolytes at -0.05 V, -0.1 V, -0.15 V, -0.2 V were diluted 20 times, while that at 0 V were diluted 10 times. As for the NO₂⁻ tests, the

post-electrolysis electrolytes at 0 V, -0.05 V, -0.1 V, -0.15 V, -0.2 V were diluted 5 times. (d) Faradaic efficiency (FE) of NH_3 and NO_2^- . Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S14 | NH_3 synthesis performance on Ru at a series of potentials. (a) Chronoamperograms of Ru at different potentials for 1 h in 0.1 mol L^{-1} NaOH and 0.1 mol L^{-1} NO_3^- . UV-Vis absorption spectra for the quantification of NH_3 (b) and NO_2^- (c). Note that for the detection of the NH_4^+ , the post-electrolysis electrolytes at 0 V, -0.05 V, -0.1 V, -0.15 V, -0.2 V were diluted 20 times. As for the NO_2^- tests, the post-electrolysis electrolytes at 0 V, -0.05 V, -0.1 V, -0.15 V, -0.2 V were diluted 2.5 times. (d) Faradaic efficiency (FE) of NH_3 and NO_2^- . Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S15 | Comparison of NO₃RR performance of various catalysts. Faradaic efficiencies (a), partial current densities of NH₃ (c), yield rate for NH₃ (d) on Co-B/Ru₁₂, Co-B/Ru₃₈, Co-B/Ru₇₅. Partial current densities of NH₃ on Co-B/Ru₁₂, Co-B, Ru (b). Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S16 | Stability test on Co-B/Ru₁₂. Chronoamperometric stability test of Co-B/Ru₁₂ at -0.1 V (vs RHE) in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻, corresponding yield rate for NH₃, and cathodic energy efficiencies for NH₃.

Supplementary Fig. S17 | Partial current density of NH₃ (J_{NH_3}) comparison. J_{NH_3} of Co-B/Ru₁₂ in different concentration of NO₃⁻ in potential range from 0V- -0.1 V (Vs. RHE). Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S18 | Stability test on Co-B/Ru₁₂. Chronoamperometric stability test of Co-B/Ru₁₂ at -0.1 V (vs RHE) in 0.5 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻, showing the partial current for NH₃ (with electrolyte replacement each 2 h).

Supplementary Fig. S19 | $^{15}\text{NH}_4^+$ detection and $^{14}\text{NH}_4^+$ quantification by ^1H NMR spectroscopy. (a) ^1H NMR spectra of the electrolytes after electrocatalysis using $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ }^{15}\text{NO}_3^-$ or $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ }^{14}\text{NO}_3^-$ in $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NaOH}$ as nitrogen source. ^1H NMR of the fresh electrolytes before electrolysis (marked as $^{15}\text{NO}_3^-$ and $^{14}\text{NO}_3^-$) are provided as controls showing no background signals of ammonia. (b) ^1H NMR spectra of different concentrations $^{14}\text{NH}_4^+$. A constant concentration of maleic acid was used as an internal standard with a proton signal at $\delta = 6.25 \text{ ppm}$. (c) Calibration curve for $^{14}\text{NH}_4^+$ detection using ^1H NMR, where the $^{14}\text{NH}_4^+$ peak area integrals were normalized by that of maleic acid. The normalized peak area integral of $^{14}\text{NH}_4^+$ is positively correlated to the concentrations of $^{14}\text{NH}_4^+$ [$^{14}\text{NH}_4^+$]. (d) Comparison of the ammonia yield rate over Co quantified by UV-Vis spectra and ^1H NMR. The electrolysis was carried out at -0.1 V (vs. RHE) for 1 h in $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NaOH}$ with $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ }^{14}\text{NO}_3^-$. Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S20 | Comparison of NO₃RR and HER on various catalysts. LSV curves of various catalyst in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH with 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻ (a) and in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH (b).

Supplementary Fig. S21 | NO₃RR and HER reaction kinetics comparison on various catalyst. Tafel slopes of various catalyst in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH with 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻ (a) and in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH (b).

Supplementary Fig. S22 | DEMS analysis. Plots showing the ion current (H₂) versus potential obtained using DEMS. The ion current is not corrected/deconvoluted.

Supplementary Fig. S23 | KIE measurements on various catalysts. LSV curves of Co-B (a), Co-B/Ru₁₂ (b), Co-B/Ru₃₈ (c), Co-B/Ru₇₅ (d), Ru (e) in an electrolyte of 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOD with 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻ in D₂O and in an electrolyte of 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH with 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NO₃⁻ in H₂O for the determination of the kinetic isotope effect (KIE) values.

Supplementary Fig. S24 | Adsorbed hydrogen (*H) analysis. Cyclic voltammograms (CV) for the determination of the *H coverage on different catalysts in Ar-saturated 0.1 M NaOH.

Supplementary Fig. S25 | Cyclic voltammograms (CV) for the determination of the double-layer capacitance of different samples in Ar-saturated 0.1 M NaOH. Co-B (a), Co-B/Ru₁₂ (b), Co-B/Ru₃₈ (c), Co-B/Ru₇₅ (d), Ru (e), and the corresponding plots of current densities against CV scan rates (f). The potentials shown in the figures are not corrected for iR drop.

Supplementary Fig. S26 | Plot of partial current for NH_3 against the KIE values of different catalysts. Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S27 | Comparison of partial current for NH_3 normalized by C_{dl} on various catalysts. (a) partial current for NH_3 normalized by C_{dl} on Co-B and Ru. (b) partial current for NH_3 normalized by C_{dl} on Co-B and Ru. Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S28 | Current density changes during chronoamperometry measurements. Plots showing the current density change ratio with respect to the value at 10 s of Co-B/Ru_x (a) and other catalysts (b) at a potential of 0 V (vs. RHE). Error bars denote the standard deviations from at least three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S29 | Morphology changes of a carbon nanoelectrode (CNE) after focus ion beam (FIB) milling. SEM images of carbon nanoelectrodes before (a) and after (b) the focus ion beam (FIB) milling process.

Supplementary Fig. S30 | Process for picking up, transferring, and placing single particle on carbon nanoelectrode. (a) Photograph of the micromanipulator set-up installed in the SEM chamber. (b) SEM images of details steps of placing single particle on carbon nanoelectrode.

Supplementary Fig. S31 | Micromanipulator inside the SEM with attached single particle and the single particle on the CNE. SEM images of a single particle of Co-B/Ru₁₂ attached to the micromanipulator tip (a,c) and single Co-B/Ru₁₂ particle placed on a carbon nanoelectrode (b,d).

CNE-1@Co-B/Ru₁₂CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂

Supplementary Fig. S32 | Morphology of single particle nanoelectrode assemblies. STEM images of CNE-1@Co-B/Ru₁₂ (a) and CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ (b) before CVs. SEM images of CNE-1@Co-B/Ru₁₂ (c) and CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ (d) after CVs.

Supplementary Fig. S33 | CV cycles on catalysts-modified carbon paper. Five CV cycles for three independent electrodes, Co-B/Ru₁₂-1 (a), Co-B/Ru₁₂-2 (b), Co-B/Ru₁₂-3 (c), in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH and 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaNO₃ with a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹.

Supplementary Fig. S34 | Structure changes of CNE-1@Co-B/Ru₁₂ after the electrocatalytic reaction. STEM images of the fabricated CNE-1@Co-B/Ru₁₂ before (a) and after 5 CV cycles (b) and the corresponding EDS mapping images before (top) and after 5 CV cycles (bottom).

Supplementary Fig. S35 | Activity change trend of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂. (a) 6th to 10th CV cycle of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH containing the 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaNO₃. (b) Plateau current ratio of 10th CV scans with respect to the 2nd CV scan of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂. Potential is not iR-corrected

Supplementary Fig. S36 | Structural evolution of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ after different CV cycles. TEM images of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ before (a), after the 5th CV cycle (b), and after the 10th CV cycle (c).

Supplementary Fig. S37 | Ru evolution of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ at different CV cycles. EDS mapping images of Ru of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ before (a), after the 5th CV cycle (b), and after the 10th CV cycle (c).

Supplementary Fig. S38 | ICP-MS determined elements concentration in 1-hour post-electrolyzed electrolyte in 0.5 mol L⁻¹ NaNO₃ at different potentials on Co-B/Ru₁₂ modified carbon paper. Concentrations of Co (a), Ru (b), and B (c) at different potentials. After 1 hour of electrolysis at 0 V (vs. RHE), all the post-electrolyzed electrolyte was collected, and the electrochemical cell was cleaned with deionized water before adding fresh electrolyte for the next potential (-0.05 V vs. RHE) electrolysis. The same collection and cleaning procedures were conducted before performing electrolysis at -0.1 V (vs. RHE). The same working electrode was used throughout the 3-stage electrolysis. Error bars denote the standard deviations from three independent measurements.

Supplementary Fig. S39 | Ru evolution of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ at different CV cycles. EDS mapping images of Co of CNE-2@Co-B/Ru₁₂ before (a), after the 5th CV cycle (b), and after the 10th CV cycle (c).

Supplementary Fig. S40 | Structure of Co-B/Ru₁₂ after reaction in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaNO₃. (a) TEM image of Co-B/Ru₁₂ after 10 hours chronoamperometry at -0.1 V (vs. RHE). (b) HRTEM image of Co-B/Ru₁₂ after 10 hours chronoamperometry at -0.1 V (vs. RHE). (c) STEM image of Co-B/Ru₁₂ after 10 hours chronoamperometry at -0.1 V (vs. RHE). (d) EDX mapping images of Co-B/Ru₁₂ after 10 hours chronoamperometry at -0.1 V (vs. RHE).

Supplementary Fig. S41 | Structure of Co-B/Ru₁₂ after reaction in 0.5 mol L⁻¹ NaNO₃. (a-c) three STEM images and corresponding EDS mapping images of Co-B/Ru₁₂ after 30 hours chronoamperometry at -0.1 V (vs. RHE).

Supplementary Fig. S42 | Electrochemical Cell for DEMS. Photograph of 3D-printed electrothermal cell with a custom-made mass-spectrometry (MS) tip.

Supplementary Table S1 | Comparison of NH₃ synthesis activity of Co-B/Ru₁₂ with other catalysts for NO₃RR at ambient conditions.

Catalysts	Electrolyte	Potential (V vs. RHE)	NH ₃ yield rate	FE _{NH₃} (%)	Double layer capacitance	Reference
Co-B/Ru ₁₂ on carbon paper	0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NaOH and 0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NaNO ₃	0.0V	7.4 ± 0.6 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	90.4 ± 9.2%	1.16 mF cm ⁻²	This work
Co-B/Ru ₁₂ on carbon paper	0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NaOH and 0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NaNO ₃	-0.2 V	15.0 ± 0.7 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	87.5± 4.8%	1.16 mF cm ⁻²	This work
Co-B/Ru ₁₂ on carbon paper	0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NaOH and 0.5mol L ⁻¹ NaNO ₃	-0.1 V	47.6± 2.7 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	83.7± 3.4%	1.16 mF cm ⁻²	This work
Pd/TiO ₂ on carbon cloth	1 mol L ⁻¹ LiCl and 0.25 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.7V	1.12 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	92.1%	5.51 mF cm ⁻²	Energy Environ. Sci. 2021, 14, 3938–3944. ¹
Cu ₂ O+Co ₃ O ₄ on carbon paper	0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NaOH and 0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NaNO ₃	-0.3V	12.76 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	85.4%	0.84 mF cm ⁻²	Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. 2023, 62, e202214830 ²
PdCu nanocube on carbon paper	1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 1 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.2V	≈1.7 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	≈72 %	3.59 mF cm ⁻²	Nat. Commun. 2022, 13, 2338 ³
Cu/CuAu ordered SAA on carbon paper	1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 1 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.2V	≈2.72 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	≈62 %	4.91 mF cm ⁻²	Nat. Synth. 2023, 2, 624 ⁴
Rh@Cu 0.6% on Cu foil	0.1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.2V	≈13.5 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	93%	N/A	Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. 2022,134, e202202556 ⁵
Co ₃ CuN on carbon paper	0.5 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 0.032 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.3V	7.74 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	97%	N/A	Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. 2023, 62, e202308775 ⁶
Ni ₃₅ /NC-sd on Ti mesh	0.5 mol L ⁻¹ Na ₂ SO ₄ and 0.3 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.5V	1.2 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	99%	N/A	Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. 2021, 60, 20711–20716 ⁷
Fe/Ni ₂ P on carbon cloth	0.2 mol L ⁻¹ K ₂ SO ₄ and 0.05 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.4V	4.16 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	94.3%	N/A	Adv. Energy Mater. 2022, 12, 2103872 ⁸
Fe SAC on glassy carbon	0.1 mol L ⁻¹ K ₂ SO ₄ and 0.5 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.66V	≈1.95 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	75%	N/A	Nat. Commun. 2021, 12, 2870 ⁹
Strained Ru nanoclusters on carbon paper	1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 1 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.2V	19.89 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	≈100%	0.48 mF cm ⁻²	J. Am. Chem. Soc. 2020, 142, 7036–7046 ¹⁰
Meso-PdN NCs on carbon paper	0.1 mol L ⁻¹ Na ₂ SO ₄ and 0.005mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.7V	0.376 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	96%	1.17 mF cm ⁻²	Adv. Mater.2023, 35, 2207305 ¹¹
Ru/Cu ₂ O on Cu foam	1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 1 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.4 V	119 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	75%	449 mF cm ⁻²	J. Am. Chem. Soc. 2024, 146, 668–676 ¹²
Ru/CuNW on Cu foam	1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 0.032 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.135 V	76.5 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	96%	740.6 mF cm ⁻²	Nat. Nanotechnol.2022, 17, 757-769 ¹³
Pd ₇₄ Ru ₂₆ on carbon fiber paper	1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 0.032 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.5 V	20.6 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	91.6%	110.8 mF cm ⁻²	Chem. Sci., 2024, 15, 8204–8215 ¹⁴
Ru-Fe ₂ O ₃ on carbon cloth	0.5 mol L ⁻¹ Na ₂ SO ₄ and 0.1 mol L ⁻¹ NO ₃ ⁻	-0.9 V	5.6 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	72:8%	4.74 mF cm ⁻²	Appl. Catal., B,2024, 351,123967 ¹⁵
Ru SASs/Co HNSs on carbon paper	1 mol L ⁻¹ NaOH and 1 mol L ⁻¹ NaNO ₃	-0.3V	8.211 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	100%	N/A	Chem. Eng. J.; 2024,490, 151883 ¹⁶
Ru SA-NC on carbon paper	1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 0.5 mol L ⁻¹ KNO ₃	-0.6 V	2.278 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	72.8%	N/A	ACS Nano, 2023, 17, 3483-3491 ¹⁷
RuOx/Pd on carbon cloth	1 mol L ⁻¹ KOH and 0.51mol L ⁻¹ KNO ₃	-0.5 V	23.5 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²	98.6%	N/A	ACS Nano, 2023, 17, 1081-1090 ¹⁸

Supplementary Table S2 | Comparison of the ammonia synthesis rate of our Co-B/Ru₁₂ electrocatalyzed NO₃RR with those of Haber-Bosch process at lab scale (milder reaction conditions) and of the state-of-the-art electrocatalytic and photocatalytic NRR routes

Ammonia synthesis route	Catalyst	NH ₃ synthesis rate	Operation condition	Reference
Haber-Bosch process	Ba ₂ RuH ₆ /MgO	35 mmol g ⁻¹ _{cat} h ⁻¹	300°C and 10 bar	Nat. Catal. 2021,11,959-967 ¹⁹
Haber-Bosch process	Ni/LaN	5.543 mmol g ⁻¹ _{cat} h ⁻¹	400°C and 1 bar	Nature 2020,7816,391-395 ²⁰
Haber Bosch process	Ru/LaCoSi	18.5 mmol g ⁻¹ _{cat} h ⁻¹	400°C and 9 bar	J. Am. Chem. Soc.2022,144,8683-8692 ²¹
N ₂ reduction reaction	Ru single atom catalysts	7.12 mmol g ⁻¹ _{cat} h ⁻¹	25°C; ambient pressure	Adv. Mater. 2018, 30, 1803498 ²²
N ₂ reduction reaction	Proton-filtering covalent organic frameworks	16.89 mmol g ⁻¹ _{cat} h ⁻¹	25°C; ambient pressure	Nat. Catal. 2021,4, 322-331 ²³
NO ₃ ⁻ reduction reaction	Co-B/Ru ₁₂	5597 mmol g ⁻¹ _{cat} h ⁻¹	25°C; ambient pressure	This work

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